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Earlier spring snowmelt drives arrowleaf balsamroot phenology in montane meadows

Ecosphere

Appendix S1: Figure S1: Schematic of the study area with plots of corresponding treatments of decreased spring snowpack via snow removal (SR: not heated, snow removal), warming via passive heating (H: heated, no removal), decreased spring snowpack and warming (H-SR: heated, snow removal), and control (C: not heated, no removal).

Appendix S1: Figure S2: Individual *Balsamorhiza sagittata* with identification tag for continued monitoring.

